

Bound Quantum Mechanics, Classical Mechanics and Flow/Flux Scheme

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In a previous note (1), we argued that both free particle quantum and classical mechanics follow from an energy flow/flux scheme based on:

$$d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1b))$$

$A(x,t)$ turns out to be the classical action $tL(v)$ (L =Lagrangian) with $x/t=v$ and the above hold for both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases.

We further argued that ((1a)) and ((1b)) lead to two sets of solutions, one classical and the other quantum. The classical solution assumes $dt \rightarrow 0$ and $dx \rightarrow 0$ i.e. flows may be followed at each point in space (and time). In (2) we argued that ((1a)) and ((1b)) are consistent with $p=dL/dv$ (partial) and $H=E= pv - L$. From these together with $p=Ev$ one may find: $E=mo/\text{sqrt}(1-vv)$ ($c=1$). For the nonrelativistic case, $E= mocc + .5mvv$. In this classical analysis one may resolve each t and x , thus if one has a function $V(x)$ (potential) representing energy, the nonrelativistic result is: $(E-V(x)) = .5mvv$.

The quantum solution to ((1a)) and ((1b)) is very different. It establishes eigenvalue equations i.e. $id/dt (\text{partial}) \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ and $-id/dx (\text{partial}) \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ for the free particle. The importance of this is that new physical mechanisms seem to come into play. $A= -Et+px$ so $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ suggests time and spatial regions proportional to $1/E$ and $1/p$ in which there is some ambiguity i.e. there are two dimensions and there seems to be some kind of probability for the particle to be in one dimension or the other at x (and similar results for t) i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. As a result, one may not have $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$. Furthermore, it is argued that a two dimensional associated probability scheme must accompany energy flow. At first this may seem strange, but if one considers a photon which has an energy flow Ev , one has electric and magnetic fields perpendicular to each other and perpendicular to the motion which undergo periodic motion linked to $\cos(wt)$ and $\sin(wt)$. Thus, the quantum particle periodic probability mimics an already known result from Maxwell's equations. In fact, we have argued that for fermions there is additional angular motion i.e. spin linked with the recognition of 3-space. Thus we argue that quantum mechanics is involved with periodic type probability motions which are needed to resolve dx and dt (linked to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$) and periodic probability motion (spin) and are also needed for fermions to resolve 3-space as two p vectors may have point in different directions (i.e. spin).

Quantum mechanics therefore seems to be a very different theory from classical mechanics, but both appear to be based on energy flow/flux. As a result, the average of a quantum bound state should be linked to a classical system we argue in this note as one only deals with energy flow/flux.

Classical System

As noted above, a classical system is based on a free particle energy flow:

$$dA/dx \text{ (partial)} = p \text{ ((1a)) and } dA/dt \text{ (partial)} = -E \text{ ((1b))}$$

with $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$. Thus one knows energy and energy flow (p) at each x, t . Furthermore in (2) we showed that $A = tL(v)$ and that using $dL/dv = p$ and $H = E = pv - L$ with $p = Ev$ one has: $E = m/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) so for the nonrelativistic case $E = m_0c^2 + .5mv^2$. As a result, one may introduce a potential $V(x)$ which represents energy at x . In such a scenario one does not need any notion of force, although one needs the idea of energy and energy flow. In such a case, the nonrelativistic result is:

$$E - V(x) = .5m v(x)v(x) \text{ ((3))}$$

Every point x, t is discerned and one knows energy and energy flow at each point. The energy flow $p = mv$ changes from x to x as does $E - V(x)$.

Quantum System

In (1) we argued that ((1a)) and ((1b)) have a second solution i.e. one in terms of eigenfunctions i.e.

$$id/dt \text{ (partial)} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \text{ ((2a)) and } -id/dx \text{ (partial)} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \text{ ((2b))}$$

At first this appears as merely a math formalism, but we argue that the physics associated with ((2a)) and ((2b)) are very different from the classical case. $\exp(iA) = \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ so instead of $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ one has $dx \rightarrow 1/p$ and $dt \rightarrow 1/E$, where $E = .5mv^2$ in the nonrelativistic case or $m/\sqrt{1-vv}$ in the relativistic. As a result, there are finite length dx and dt regions in quantum mechanics depending on energy and energy flow. Furthermore, within these regions there is an unusual two dimensional periodic probability scheme linked to $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. The modulus is 1 to ensure probability is conserved at 1 i.e. 1 particle. Thus discernment of dx and dt is based on changing probabilities and this is directly linked to energy flow i.e. p . One no longer has the classical scenario of a particle simply translating in space in time $v = x/t$ (free particle). Matters are even more complicated as we argue that there is further probabilistic motion associated with fermions and linked to discerning 3-space i.e. spin. At first this may seem unusual, but Maxwell's equations for a photon already show that one has periodic motion associated with E and B fields (i.e. linked to $\sin(-\omega t + kx)$) which are perpendicular to p and to each other. In other words a photon does not simply represent energy translation as energy flux. Much more occurs related to this motion. First there is spin linked to the spin matrix e_{ijk} (see (2)) and then there is $dx \rightarrow 1/p$ and $dt \rightarrow 1/E$ where $E = pc$ because there is a wavelength and frequency. Thus the ideas linked to the second solution of ((1a)) and ((1b)) are not so unusual as they are already present in electromagnetic theory.

Quantum Bound States with a Potential

The quantum result above was established for a free particle only, using ((1a)) and ((1b)). What does one do if there is a potential $V(x)$ representing energy at specific x points if one does not want to think in terms of forces? First of all, the quantum free particle result is based on flow/flux for a particular E and p with dx , dt regions depending on $1/E$ and $1/p$. This contradicts the idea of a $V(x)$ which is defined at all x points i.e. $dx \rightarrow 0$. It seems one may consider a statistical solution i.e. an average kinetic energy linked to various $\exp(ipx)$ terms. How should such an average be calculated?

Consider a point x . This is part of wavelength regions associated with $\exp(ip_1 x)$, $\exp(ip_2 x)$, $\exp(ip_3 x)$ etc. The kinetic energy from each of these is $p_i^2/2m$, but the two dimensional probability weights $\cos(p_i x)$ and $\sin(p_i x)$ differ for a specific x . If one considers these to be probabilities which add in OR situations, and one associates $p_i^2/2m$ which each dimension multiplied by the probability $\cos(p_i x)$ or $\sin(p_i x)$ one has:

$$\left\{ \sum_j p_j^2/2m a_j \cos(p_j x) + i \sum_j p_j^2 a_j \sin(p_j x) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_j a_j \cos(p_j x) + i \sum_j a_j \sin(p_j x) \right\} \quad ((4))$$

where a_j is a weight for $\exp(ip_j x)$. In such a scenario one may map a point found at different phase points within the various wavelengths to an absolute point x in space. This result, however, only represents an average or is linked to $v_{rms}(x)$. Thus, the idea of absolute x space seems to be linked to quantum averages at least in the quantum picture. The quantum average energy flow/flux scheme, however, should yield the classical energy flow/flux scheme because both pictures are based on the idea of energy flow/flux. As a result:

$$[-1/2m \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) p^2/2m] / [\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)] = E - V(x) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is the bound state Schrodinger equation as we consider the nonrelativistic case. (For the Klein-Gordon case, the analysis in this note would lead to $E \rightarrow E - V(x)$.) ((5)) has important consequences because only discrete E values satisfy the equation. Thus the energy flow/flux average picture only holds for special resonance energies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may obtain both classical and quantum free particle solutions from ((1a)) and ((1b)) energy flow/flux equations. For the classical case $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ while for the quantum $dx \rightarrow 1/p$ and $dt \rightarrow 1/E$. Furthermore, $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ in the quantum case suggests an unusual two dimensional periodic probability scheme associated with energy flow i.e. p (momentum). This becomes more unusual for fermions where there is further probability flow i.e. angular momentum or spin associated with 3-space discernment. Thus, energy flow which is simply translation in the classical case is complicated in the quantum. If one adds a potential $V(x)$ to a quantum scenario, one immediately has a problem because $V(x)$ is defined at each x with $dx \rightarrow 0$. It seems that to link quantum free particles, without using any notion of force (only energy flow), one needs to take an average using the recipe given in ((4)). Then one may obtain

the time-independent Schrodinger equation (or Klein-Gordon equation with $E \rightarrow E - V(x)$). This equation is linked to average energy i.e. average kinetic energy $KE(x) = E - V(x)$ which is identical to the classical picture except for the fact that in the quantum case one is only dealing with averages. One may note, however, that the quantum average picture only holds for a discrete set of E values unlike the classical flow picture which holds for all E .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Ruggeri Lagrangian/Action Formalism As a Flow Scheme (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Ruggeri Special Relativity From Nonrelativistic Lagrangian Formalism? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)